

Comparative Relationship between Professional Practices and Job Effectiveness among Secondary School Teachers in Abia State, Nigeria

Onwuhanze, Jude Uche¹
ifejudeinterio1979@gmail.com

Ezikpe Ngozi Nnenna¹
ngoziezikpe1@gmail.com

Douglas Peter¹

¹Educational Management; College of Education, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria

Abstract

This study examined teacher professional practices and job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Abia State, Nigeria. To achieve this purpose, two null hypotheses were raised to guide the study and correlational research design was used. The study was conducted in public secondary schools in Abia State. The population of this study was 7,453 teachers in the 246 public senior secondary schools in the state. Sample size of 739 teachers were sampled from 102 secondary schools in the state through stratified sampling technique. A researcher-developed instrument titled “Teacher Professional Practices and Job Effectiveness Questionnaire with reliability coefficient of 0.78 was used for data collection. Simple linear regression was used in analyzing the data at .05 alpha level. The findings showed that teachers’ participation in conferences and teachers’ collaboration with others significantly predicted job effectiveness. Based on the findings of this study, the conclusion made was that teachers’ professional practices like teachers’ participation in conferences and teachers’ collaboration predicted their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Abia State. Recommendations were made that teachers should always attend conferences in order to equip themselves with contemporary pedagogical practices in the teaching profession and their area of specialization because it would help them to teach effectively. Teachers should also collaborate among themselves because it would make them to be informed and acquainted with modern educational practices that lead to effective teaching.

Keywords: Teacher professional practices, job effectiveness

Introduction

Secondary school education equipped students with personal and professional development for life, and help them get ready for tertiary education. It does not only give students’ academic foundation but also teaches them important life skills, ethical principle and critical thinking techniques. It also contributes to national development by equipping individuals with the knowledge, skills, and values necessary for economic growth as well as technological advancement and social progress (Iyejare, 2023). Learners at this level of education needs to be assisted by any means possible to acquire knowledge and skills needed for effective transition to the next stage of life. It is expected that at the completion of this level of education, the learner should be able to proceed to tertiary institution, or other skill acquisition programme of their choice having learned socially acceptable behaviours, and have acquired knowledge and skills that could help them function in the labour market.

These expectations may not be realistic without the input of a teacher. This is because teachers play crucial role in the realization of educational philosophy of the nation due to their direct involvement in pedagogical activities at schools. Teachers are conventionally the ones who impart knowledge and guidance to learners. A teacher engages in developing learners psychomotor, cognitive and affective domain in formal school system, more so the teacher is a person who has undergone approved professional training in education at appropriate level capable of imparting knowledge, attitude and skills to the learners. It is the duty of the teacher to impart knowledge to learners, and are the ability to apply what they have learnt in real life situations. Thus, there is need for the teachers to be effective in their job delivery.

Effectiveness concentrates more on output, quality, quantity, efforts and cost put in. It is attaining the highest possible outcome while consuming minimum factors of input (Kindi, 2020). Effectiveness is concerned with the efficiency, which essentially consists in doing the right thing with noticeable results. Teacher job effectiveness is the extent to which a teacher qualitatively and efficiently carries his/her duties in achieving aims and objectives of the school over a period of time. It is measured in terms of the levels of teacher efficiency in pedagogical approaches like lesson preparation and presentation, job commitment, competence, mastery of the subject matter, and other curricular activities.

Teacher job effectiveness has a strategic and essential role in realizing quality education. It is generally measured by work results in the form of quantity, quality and timeliness of teachers in completing their work in planning, teaching, implementing learning plans, implementing curriculum contents, conducting evaluations and giving feedbacks. Teacher job effectiveness has to do with quality of teaching and learning in its entirety. It addresses the issues of how the teacher delivers the lesson and the influence of such lessons on the learners, (that is, learning outcomes) Osamwomyi (2016). Furthermore, teacher job effectiveness is the way the teacher manages (that is, plans, executes, monitors and evaluates) teaching and learning processes using set standards and objectives (Ukaigwe & Onwumere, 2018). Again, teacher job effectiveness measures the extent to which the teachers carry out their out-of-classroom activities such as teachers' commitment to work, regularity and punctuality, interpersonal relationship with principals and students, and preparation of notes of lesson.

There are many factors that may influence teacher job effectiveness. Such factors include teacher professional practices. Professional practices, according to Ukaigwe and Onwumere (2018), is a personal function of teachers which is meant to bring about regular update of teachers' knowledge and insight assist in identifying their potential so as to raise their professional standard in order to support the overall development of learners. Mulgas and Tagadiad (2023) opined that teachers' professional practices are the activities that develop teachers' skills, knowledge, competence, and other characteristics of teachers. Teacher professional practices are those activities designed to enhance the knowledge, skills, perception and attitudes of teachers so that they may, in turn improve the learning of students, and be more effective and satisfied in various other aspects of their work. It involves a continuous process of reflective learning and active efforts to further a teacher's knowledge and skills leading to enhanced teaching practices that positively influence students' learning outcome. Ojugo and Olubor (2021) stated that when teachers are involved in developing effective professional practices, they are equipped with desired knowledge, skills and abilities to achieve educational goals.

Teacher professional practices include teacher participation in conferences and teachers' collaborations with others. A conference is a formal meeting where participants in a particular area exchange ideas in various topics. A conference, according to Osamwonyi (2016) is an academic gathering in which certain speakers come prepared, often by invitation or a fee, to open discussion to some reasonably interesting or controversial topics or theme. Generally, conference attendants come to listen, questions the main speakers, make additional prepared or spontaneous contributions to the discussion, evaluate opinions and points of view, and discuss formally and informally among themselves. Rimmer and Floyd (2020) stated that conferences are activities within a field and of the commitment of individuals to their own practice and the sphere in which they operate. A conference could be made up of paper presentations, series of sessions featuring multiple independent speakers. The sessions could cover more than one day as this allows more opportunities for social interaction, whether through evening activities or informal liaison as well as technical session.

Presentations are usually followed by discussions. Conference ideally suggests discussions among persons of similar experiential exposure to the topic of discussion for the purpose of reaching agreements in controversial issues (Akpan and Ita, 2015). Teachers could suffer from instructional planning and delivery if they do not attend conferences. Ibrahim (2021) held that participation in conferences promote effectiveness and efficiency of teachers in teaching for the betterment of learners and the schools. According to Anho and Akpokiniovo (2023), conference in education entails the coming together of diverse persons who are experts in different areas of education with a view to sharing of idea. Through conferences, teachers have access to a large range of information which, by extension transform to enhance effectiveness in the teaching and learning processes.

On the other hand, collaboration is the act of working with another person or group of people to produce a meaningful outcome. Mora-Ruano *et al.* (2019) defined collaboration as an interactive process that enable people with diverse expertise to generate creative ideas and solutions to mutually defined problem. Teacher collaboration deals with continuous unity of active and regular interaction and sharing of ideas and activities among teachers for improved teaching and learning. Teacher collaboration is also aimed at enhancing relational trust, school administration, as well as coordination and exchange of ideas and materials among teachers for teaching effectiveness (Mora-Ruano *et al.*, 2019). Collaboration is voluntary, requires parity and understanding among teachers, is based on mutual goals, depend on shared responsibility for participation and decision-making. Teachers who collaborate share their resources and share accountability for outcomes.

Teacher collaboration is the joint interaction of two or more teachers in activities that are needed to perform their teaching job effectively (Zhang *et al.*, 2023). Teachers who engaged in collaborative activities tend to gain higher teaching confidence and reduce the sense of isolation compared with teachers working alone (Reeves *et al.*, 2017). Collaboration equips teachers with opportunities to discuss, debate, observe and share information methods and procedures (Vangrieken *et al.*, 2020). According to Reeves *et al.* (2017), through collaboration, formation of a friendly partnership is ensured which can promote teachers' knowledge, information and emotion, sharing and then improve teachers' teaching effectiveness. It is

essential that colleagues support each other. Unity among the teachers will give a significant impact to schools, as they will embody unity and sense of responsibility of all of their actions (Balugos & Rivera, 2019). According to Zhang *et al.* (2023), the nature of teachers' work requires them to carry out effective collaboration with others, share knowledge and information, exchange and interact cooperatively so as to promote individual abilities to teach effectively.

Caskey and Carpenter (2014) noted that strong collaboration and collaborative cultures develop overtime require honesty and commitment to the process. While the benefits are clear, genuine collaboration is complex. Patience in the moment and anticipation for the outcome can lead to deep teacher learning that translates into tangible learners' achievement. Teachers can develop authentic collaborative groups in which they address common issues, shared goals or school-wide initiatives; engage in mutually beneficial endeavors using communal resources; and advance their skills, knowledge, and disposition related to student learning. Moreover, in order to successfully implement innovative, student-centered, and collaborative learning methods, proficient collaboration among teachers is the secret.

Education is a never-ending process. It does not stop after earning a degree and starting a career. Through professional practices, teachers can constantly improve their skills update knowledge and become more effective in the teaching profession. Amierogan and Unachukwu (2021) asserted that regardless of teachers training and level of education, there is the need for every teacher to constantly and regularly renew, upgrade and expand his/her skill, knowledge and ability as well as capability. Teacher professional practices may be necessary for teachers as quality assurance strategies to ensure that teachers become highly competent in their job execution. This is because, any teacher that is not growing in skills and knowledge cannot keep pace with his/her relationship with the teaching profession. According to Amadi and Oscaat (2021), teachers' professional practices are important because of the need for teachers to perform well and raise academic performance of students in the school system. In other to accomplish this task in their jobs, in this technological and innovation driven era, teachers must rise up and upgrade their knowledge, skills and practices. Therefore, this background necessitated this study on teacher professional practices and job effectiveness in secondary schools in Abia State, Nigeria.

It has been observed that teachers in secondary schools in Abia State work too independently without effective teamwork and lack of participation in conferences (Akpan et al 2015). This kind of situation results in poor teaching and learning in the schools (Ibrahim, 2021). Due to the fast pace of changes in the educational sector and demands in the economic sector, as well as utilization of technological gadgets in teaching and learning, teachers now face new challenges in teaching and learning (Rimmer and Floyd 2020). Thus, to cope with these challenges of conference attendance and collaboration, more improved and effective professional practices may be important for teachers to teach effectively in secondary schools (Osamwomyi, 2016). Hence, to solve this problem, this study was undertaken to examined teacher professional practices and job effectiveness in secondary schools in Abia State, Nigeria. The outcome of this research will enhance teachers' professionalism in Abia State.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine if teacher professional practices predict job effectiveness in secondary schools in Abia State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. Examine if teachers' participation in conferences predict their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Abia State.
2. Determine if teachers' collaboration predicts their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Abia State.

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between conference participation and job effectiveness among secondary school Teachers in Abia State

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between collaboration and job effectiveness among secondary school Teachers in Abia State

Methodology

Correlational research design was adopted for this study. This design examines the relationship between two or more variables and enable the investigator to ascertain the degree to which variations in one variable are caused by variations in another variables. The study was conducted in public secondary schools in Abia State, Nigeria. The population of the study was 7,453 teachers in the 246 public secondary schools in the state. The study used the teachers as participants since they are major stakeholders in the attainment of educational objectives and aims. A sample size of 745 teachers, which is 10 percent of the population of teachers was sampled from 102 secondary schools in the state. The sample size was selected using stratified sampling technique. A researcher-developed instrument known as "Teacher Professional Practices and Job

Effectiveness Questionnaire (TPPJEQ)” was used for data collection. The instrument has 45 items with declarative statements; 15 items each measured teachers’ participation in conferences, teachers’ collaboration and job effectiveness on a 4-point scale of strongly agree (4) agree (3) disagree (2) strongly disagree (1point).

The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by three experts, two in Department of Educational Management and one from Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Science Education, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State. The experts were required to assess if the items measure the variables used in the study. Cronbach alpha method was employed to estimate the reliability coefficient of the instrument. Fifty respondents who did not take part in the main study were randomly selected and the instrument administered on them. A reliability coefficient of 0.78 was obtained for the instrument. The instrument was considered reliable for use in conducting the study. The researcher was assisted by research assistants to administer the instrument to the respondents. Out of the 745 copies of the instrument administered, 739 copies were retrieved from the respondents, and were used for the data analysis. Simple linear regression was used in analyzing the data at .05 alpha level. The magnitude of coefficient of correlation provided by Udoh (2019) was employed, which states that .00 to .20 shows very weak relationship, .21 to .40 indicates weak relationship, .41 to .60 shows moderate relationship, .61 to .80 indicates strong relationship and .81 to 0.99 shows very strong relationship. In testing the null hypotheses, the probability value (p-value) was compared with 0.05 alpha level. If the p-value is less than or equal to .05 ($p \leq 0.05$), the null hypotheses were rejected. However, if the probability value is greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$), the null hypotheses were not rejected.

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between conference participation and job effectiveness among secondary school Teachers in Abia State

Simple linear regression was used in testing hypothesis one as indicated in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of simple regression analysis of the extent to which teachers’ participation in conferences predict their job effectiveness

Variables	R	B	R ²		
Teachers’ participation in conferences (X)	.610	.441	.372		
Job effectiveness (Y)					
Sources of variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	47.947	1	47.947	541.475	.000
Residual	34.623	738	.089		
Total	82.570	739			

*Significant at $P < .05$, $n = 739$

The result in Table 1 indicates if teachers’ participation in conferences does not significantly predict their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools. The coefficient of correlation (R) of .610 indicates a strong relationship between teachers’ participation in conferences and job effectiveness. The beta weight of .441 shows that for every unit increase in teachers’ participation in conferences, job effectiveness increases positively by .441. Also, the coefficient of determination (R²) value of .372 shows that teachers’ participation in conferences contributes 37.2 percent to job effectiveness. The result also indicates that F-value of 541.475 with 1 and 739 degrees of freedom at .05 alpha level is significant. Since the p-value of .000 is lower than the alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis, which states that teachers’ participation in conferences, does not significantly predict job effectiveness is rejected. Hence, teachers’ participation in conferences does not significantly predict their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Abia State.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between collaboration and job effectiveness among secondary school Teachers in Abia State

Simple linear regression was used in testing hypothesis two as indicated in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of simple regression analysis of the extent to which teachers’ collaboration predict their job effectiveness

Variables	R	B	R ²
Teachers’ collaboration (X)	.608	.430	.369

Sources of variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	49.341	1	28.303	1233.033	.000
Residual	37.867	738	.023		
Total	88.629	739			

*Significant at $P < .05$, $n = 739$

The result in Table 2 indicates if teachers’ collaboration does not significantly predict their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools. The coefficient of correlation (R) of .608 indicates a strong relationship between teachers’ collaboration and job effectiveness. The beta weight of .430 shows that for every unit increase in teachers’ collaboration, job effectiveness increases positively by .430. Also, the coefficient of determination (R²) value of .369 shows that collaboration contributes 36.9 percent to job effectiveness. The result also indicates that F-value of 1233.033 with 1 and 739 degrees of freedom at .05 alpha level is significant. Since the p-value of .000 is lower than the alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis, which states that teachers’ collaboration, does not significantly predict job effectiveness is rejected. Hence, teachers’ collaboration does not significantly predict their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Abia State.

Discussion of Findings

The result of hypothesis one showed that teachers’ participation in conferences significantly predicted their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Abia State. This result implies that conferences can help teachers in improvement of subject matter knowledge, assist in management task, lend a hand to improving reciprocal respect among instructors and identify the need of contemporary teaching methods. This finding agrees with that of Ibrahim (2021) who found that participation in conferences promote effectiveness of teachers in teaching for the betterment of students and schools. Teachers should not confide only in the four walls of the classroom, but they have to be allowed to keep abreast to work with other people in the community aside from doing daily routines in education. Teachers have to engage themselves in planning their own professional development on a continuous basis to cope with the continuous change. The finding is also in agreement with that of Anho and Akpokiniovo (2023) because they reported that through conferences, teachers have access to a large range of information via conferences, which by extension transform to enhance effectiveness in the teaching and learning processes.

Furthermore, to take care of the inadequacies of pre-service teacher preparation, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2018) in the National Policy on Education made provision for development of teachers by stating that teacher education shall continue to take cognizance of the changes in methodology and in the curriculum, and that conference programmes for teachers and head teachers shall be regulated. This therefore, emphasizes the importance and the need for every teacher to be constantly renewed, updated and upgraded in his or her knowledge and practices. The objective of teacher participation in conferences is to enhance improvement and help to abreast them with the latest innovation in their field. This would assist in the improvement of instructional abilities, and keep them informed on new facts in education.

The result of hypothesis two indicated that teachers’ collaboration significantly predicted their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Abia State. This result implies that through collaboration, teachers can have more opportunities to reflect on their teaching practices, assess if what they are doing works and accordingly change or reinforce their actions and behaviors in the classrooms. This finding agrees with that of Reeves et al. (2017) as they reported that through collaboration, formation of a friendly partnership is ensured which can promote teachers’ knowledge, information and emotion sharing and then improve teachers’ teaching effectiveness. Through collaboration, teachers are able to adopt new teaching strategies and in turn allow teachers to gain confidence, think critically and reflect about their teaching practices. Increase in the quality of collaboration can lead to school improvement and show that students’ achievement is higher in schools with strong collaborative environments. This finding is also in line with that of Zhang *et al.* (2023) because they found that collaboration with other teachers enable them to share knowledge, exchange and interact cooperatively so as to promote individual abilities to teach effectively. In order to create thriving collaboration communities and specification of

goals, teachers should allocate sufficient time to collaborate. Teacher collaboration is an important aspect of teacher's professional lives, because it is a means to continuously reflect on and improve the practice of teaching.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the conclusion made was that teachers' professional practices like teachers' participation in conferences and teachers' collaboration predicted their job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Abia State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. Teachers should always attend conferences in order to equip themselves with contemporary pedagogical practices in the teaching profession.
2. Teachers should collaborate among themselves because it would make them to be informed and acquainted with modern educational practices that lead to effective teaching.

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